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Deep learning based reconstructions of the Atlantic meridional
overturning circulation confirm twenty-first century declineSimon L L Michel^{1,2,*} , Henk A Dijkstra¹ , Francesco Guardamagna¹ , Valérian Jacques-Dumas¹ ,
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E-mail: simon.michel@physics.ox.ac.uk**Keywords:** AMOC reconstruction, machine learning, climate models validationSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)**Abstract**

Gaining knowledge of the past and present variations of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC) is crucial for the development of accurate future climate projections. The short range covered by direct AMOC observations, inconsistent paleoclimate records, and scattered hydrographic data are insufficient to realistically reconstruct the AMOC strength since 1900. An AMOC proxy index based on sea surface temperatures suggests that the AMOC has declined by 15% since the late 19th century but this index received extensive scientific criticism. Here, we use a deep learning algorithm and climate model simulations to accurately reconstruct the AMOC strength between 20° N and 60° N since 1900. In contrast with the existing indices, our reconstructions are well in agreement with AMOC strength variations simulated by climate models and direct observations at 26.5° N. Our novel set of AMOC reconstructions contribute to a larger confidence in 21st century AMOC decline projections from climate models.

Modern earth system models (ESMs) from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase 6 (CMIP6) (Eyring *et al* 2016) consistently project a decline in Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC) strength throughout the twenty-first century (Weijer *et al* 2020) due to anthropogenic climate change (Eyring *et al* 2021). However, there is substantial spread in projected AMOC decline among ESMs (Weijer *et al* 2020, Bellomo *et al* 2021), with a strong meridional dependency (Frajka Williams *et al* 2019, Zou *et al* 2020, Årthun *et al* 2023, Asbjørnsen *et al* 2024), leading to uncertainties in regional and global temperature and precipitation trends (Bellomo *et al* 2021). Given the implications for policymaking, robust validation of ESMs using historical observations is essential, particularly regarding AMOC strength (Bellomo *et al* 2021).

The AMOC has been monitored at 26.5° N since 2004 through the RAPID array (Cunningham *et al* 2007, Smeed *et al* 2014, McCarthy *et al* 2015, 2018, Moat *et al* 2023), providing a valuable nearly 20 year observational record (Moat *et al* 2023). Although this dataset reveals significant variations in AMOC

strength (Smeed *et al* 2014, 2018), it is limited by measuring the large-scale circulation at only one latitude. To address this limitation, subsequent research projects such as SAMBA (Meinen *et al* 2013) and OSNAP (Lozier *et al* 2019) have begun measuring AMOC at other latitudes (34° S and 60° N, respectively), albeit with shorter time series of less than ten years. Nevertheless, the RAPID observations, referred to as AMOC_{RAPID}, indicate an overall decline in AMOC strength since 2004 (Smeed *et al* 2014, 2018), though there has been a modest but consistent increase in the last twelve years of available data (Smeed *et al* 2018, Moat *et al* 2023) (i.e. from 2010 to 2021). However, due to their expense and complexity (Cunningham *et al* 2007, Smeed *et al* 2014, McCarthy *et al* 2015, 2018, Moat *et al* 2023), the RAPID measurements cover too short a period to establish or dismiss any consistent long-term trend in AMOC intensity in response to anthropogenic climate change (Cunningham *et al* 2007, Smeed *et al* 2014, McCarthy *et al* 2015, 2018, Frajka-Williams *et al* 2019, Moat *et al* 2023). Recent studies, incorporating direct deep ocean observations from various

Atlantic regions (Lozier *et al* 2019, Chafik *et al* 2022, Asbjørnsen *et al* 2024), hydrographic data (Rossby *et al* 2022), and ESMs (Zou *et al* 2020), have highlighted the latitudinal dependency of AMOC variability, thereby casting doubt on the robustness of trends observed in RAPID data (Moat *et al* 2023).

Subsurface density measurements in coastal North Atlantic areas have been utilised to contextualise direct AMOC observations (Worthington *et al* 2021, Rossby *et al* 2022). However, due to their limited spatial and temporal coverage, these data are too noisy to effectively reconstruct monthly to annual AMOC strength using current aggregation methods (Rossby *et al* 2022). Given the constraints of using AMOC_{RAPID} and hydrographic observations for ESM validation, AMOC fingerprints based on North Atlantic sea surface temperature (SST) and salinity (SSS) fields have been developed to estimate 20th-century AMOC variations (Knight *et al* 2005, Caesar *et al* 2018, Zhang *et al* 2019, Jackson and Wood 2020). Notably, the emergence of the ‘warming hole’ pattern in the North Atlantic subpolar gyre (SPG) surface has been identified as an indicator of declining AMOC strength since 1900 (Rahmstorf *et al* 2015, Caesar *et al* 2018). Using the SST average over the SPG (SST_{SPG}) minus the global mean SST signal as an AMOC proxy (AMOC_{SPG}, see material and methods), it has been demonstrated that the AMOC decreased by 15% overall since the mid-19th century (Caesar *et al* 2018). However, salinity also significantly contributes to surface density fields and is thus critical for AMOC variations (Jackson and Wood 2020). In this regard, SSS indices instead reveal a century-long upward trend in AMOC strength (figure S1), raising doubts about the relevance of sea surface-based AMOC indices.

Although an abnormally cold (resp. warm) SST_{SPG} can indicate a decreasing (resp. increasing) AMOC response to anthropogenic greenhouse gas (resp. aerosol) emissions, the respective timescales of SST_{SPG} and AMOC responses to overlapping and opposite radiative effects from different forcings differ considerably and are non-stationary (Little *et al* 2020). The AMOC_{SPG} index also assumes that the AMOC fingerprint on SST_{SPG} over the strongly forced recent decades (Caesar *et al* 2018) was the same as during the mainly naturally driven AMOC over the 20th century (Latif *et al* 2022). This constitutes a strong assumption of stationarity in SPG and AMOC dynamics under constantly evolving radiative forcing (Little *et al* 2020). North Atlantic SST and SST_{SPG} are also driven by diverse factors and their interactions, including the AMOC (Knight *et al* 2005, Zhang *et al* 2019, Jackson and Wood 2020), but also stratospheric (Booth *et al* 2012, Mann *et al* 2021) and tropospheric (Booth *et al* 2012) aerosol concentrations, or atmospheric (Fan *et al* 2023) and oceanic (Buckley and Marshall 2016, Frajka-Williams *et al* 2019, Chafik *et al* 2022, Swingedouw *et al* 2022, Chafik and Lozier 2025) processes. Given the variety

of processes affecting North Atlantic SST patterns, the AMOC_{SPG} may be too simplistic as its calculation assumes an unrealistic in-phase and stationary relationship between SST_{SPG}, the AMOC, and the global warming signal (Chen and Tung 2021) (figure S2).

Consequently, the Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate (2019) from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Collins *et al* 2019) evaluated the claim that the AMOC strength has significantly decreased as a response to climate change (Caesar *et al* 2018) with only *medium confidence*. With respect to the AMOC validation of ESMs, the AMOC_{SPG} indicates that the AMOC has declined over the second half of the 20th century (Caesar *et al* 2018), while the mean of the CMIP6 ESMs indicates that it would have increased (Menary *et al* 2020, Robson *et al* 2022). Are the CMIP6 ESMs, with their known biases, wrong here or is the AMOC_{SPG}, often considered as extended AMOC observations (Caesar *et al* 2018, Boers 2021, Ditlevsen and Ditlevsen 2023), inadequate? Clearly, there is an urgency to obtain better reconstructions of the 20th-century AMOC strength (figure S1), using available observations.

1. A deep learning approach to AMOC reconstruction

Here, we provide a novel reconstruction of the AMOC strength using a deep learning algorithm trained to produce AMOC timeseries at different latitudes based on SST observations. The use of deep learning for this task is innovative, as is the production of several AMOC indices for different latitudes of the North Atlantic Ocean (figure 1(a)). This aligns with recent results indicating a strong spatial dependence of AMOC variability from interannual to decadal timescales (Zou *et al* 2020, Asbjørnsen *et al* 2024). These findings are confirmed for our North Atlantic study area (0° N–80° N, 80° W–0°, figure 1(a)) by a set of 51 historical climate simulations from 17 ESMs (3 simulations each, table S1). This extensive model intercomparison analysis indicates that AMOC trends (figure 1(b)) and covariances (figure 1(c)) in the North Atlantic meridional stream function time series vary greatly across latitudes (Zou *et al* 2020, Asbjørnsen *et al* 2024) and depth (figures 1(b) and (c)). This analysis further confirms that AMOC variations cannot be characterised by a single index, suggesting that former attempts to reconstruct the AMOC strength from surface data can potentially lead to misinterpretations regarding historical AMOC variability.

The deep learning method we use here is a 3-layer (convolutional neural network (CNN), see materials and methods), a widely used approach in image analysis (Goodfellow *et al* 2016) that has proven itself in many climate research applications (Ham *et al* 2019, Jacques-Dumas *et al* 2022, Bône *et al* 2024). To train

CNN models, we selected the best ESM from the 17 listed in table S1 for representing the two main components of surface density fields: the SST and SSS fields (table S2). The model-observation comparison uses SST and SSS observations from the EN4 dataset (Good *et al* 2013). To comprehensively study ESMs' ability to represent SST and SSS, we computed mean biases in simulated mean state, standard deviations, minima, and maxima over the overlapping period of historical CMIP6 simulations and the EN4 dataset (1900–2014, figure S3). These statistics were averaged over three historical simulations for each of the 17 ESMs (table S2).

We focus on model biases calculated from annually averaged data (figure S3) and also provide similar analyses for monthly and seasonal averages for both SST (figure S4) and SSS (figure S5). Results indicate that ESMs can better represent SST only, SSS only, or both, in comparison to other ESMs (figures S3–S5 and table S2). We are interested in the ESM that best reproduces statistics for both SST and SSS, as they together determine surface density fields which is crucial for simulating the interplay between the ocean surface and the AMOC (Knight *et al* 2005, Zhang *et al* 2019, Jackson and Wood 2020, Swingedouw *et al* 2022). Accurately simulating SST and SSS statistical

properties is fundamental for adequately training CNN models to reconstruct the AMOC from ocean surface properties within climate simulations, which we will then apply to observational data. Additionally, while mean and variability statistics are essential for training CNNs on realistic simulation data, we also evaluated how well ESMs reproduce SST and SSS trends over the historical period (figure S6 and table S3).

2. Novel AMOC reconstructions across latitudes

The best-performing ESM identified through our bias analyses (figures S3–S6, Tabs. S2 and S3, see materials and methods) is HadGEM3-GC31-MM (hereafter HadGEM3), based on both mean-state statistics (figures S3–S5 and table S2) and trend performance (figure S6 and table S3). To train the CNNs, we use 4 historical HadGEM3 simulations, each covering 115 years (1900–2014). Additionally, we use one future simulation with low CO₂ emissions (SSP1-2.6, 86 years) and one piControl simulation (500 years) with constant pre-industrial CO₂ levels (280 ppm). Using SSP1-2.6 and piControl simulations has two

main advantages: i) it provides more data for training than the relatively short historical simulations, with greenhouse gas concentrations similar to late (SSP1-2.6) and early (piControl) historical levels; ii) it prevents CNNs from overfitting to historical climate simulations' outputs, generated under similar radiative forcing (*i.e.* observed anthropogenic and natural forcings since 1900). In addition to validations for HadGEM3, we applied the same CNN approach to the six best ESMs from figures S3–S5 and table S2 to ensure our results are not model-specific. A detailed description of climate simulations used for CNN validations and training is given in table S4 (HadGEM3 only) and table S5 (six best ESMs).

To quantify the efficiency of CNNs in reconstructing AMOC variations in HadGEM3 simulations across latitudes from 20° N to 60° N (figure 1(a)), we excluded one historical simulation from the training set at a time and trained CNNs with the remaining simulations (historical, piControl, and SSP1-2.6). The CNN's ability to reconstruct historical AMOC variations was tested by reconstructing the AMOC time series of the excluded historical member and comparing it with the original AMOC time series from this simulation (see table S4). Similarly, in the six best ESMs experiment, we applied a leave-one-model-out approach: all simulations from a single ESM are excluded from training, one ESM at a time, and the CNN's reconstruction skill is evaluated by reconstructing the historical AMOC time series from the excluded ESM (see table S5).

To ensure high performance for each CNN model trained for each excluded historical simulation and each latitude studied, we used 5-fold cross-validations (see materials and methods) to tune the CNNs' hyperparameters. We trained and tuned 109 CNNs without optimising the number of epochs. Instead, we used a large number of epochs (*i.e.* 1000) with an early stopping criterion to ensure convergence of CNNs' training losses. Therefore, we only optimised the batch sizes and initial learning rates. Each CNN was tested for three batch sizes and four initial learning rates (see supplementary materials), resulting in 12 hyperparameter combinations for each excluded historical member/latitude pair. The optimal batch size and initial learning rate for each case are provided in table S6 for HadGEM3 analyses and in table S7 for analyses based on the six best ESMs.

In order to assess the generalisability of our approach, we conducted an additional sensitivity analysis on the input variables using the six best ESMs (table S5). Applying the validation setup for the six best ESMs described above and employing single-input CNNs based on SST only, SSS only, and two-input CNNs combining both SST and SSS, we find that CNN models perform better in reconstructing historical ESM-based AMOC time series using SST

only (figure S7). This outcome might stem from significant biases and differences in ESM representations of North Atlantic SSS (Liu *et al* 2017). Moreover, utilising SST only for CNN training may yield more accurate reconstructions when applied to real data for practical reasons. Indeed, SST has been directly measured with better spatio-temporal coverage since 1900 (Good *et al* 2013) compared to SSS, making it less susceptible to measurement uncertainties and statistical approximations (Good *et al* 2013, Ben-Yami *et al* 2023).

To further assess the performance of CNN models in reconstructing ESM-based AMOC variations across latitudes, we compared our outputs with existing AMOC indices (Boers 2021, Caesar *et al* 2018, Jackson and Wood 2020) (figure S1) computed from the same historical ESM simulations. These indices include $AMOC_{SPG}$ based on SST (Caesar *et al* 2018) and four SSS-based AMOC indices computed as averages over different Atlantic areas (Jackson and Wood 2020, Boers 2021), denoted here as $AMOC_{SSS1}$ through $AMOC_{SSS4}$ (see materials and methods). In figure 2, we demonstrate that AMOC time series generated from CNN models largely outperform other AMOC indices across all latitudes studied and for the four excluded members from training (figures 2(a)–(d)). While $AMOC_{SSS3}$ and $AMOC_{SSS4}$ exhibit low performance in estimating AMOC strength at any latitude for all four historical members (figures 2(a)–(d)), SPG-based SSS ($AMOC_{SSS1}$ and $AMOC_{SSS2}$) and SST ($AMOC_{SPG}$) indices show relatively good abilities in estimating variations of southernmost AMOC time series for two members (members 2 and 4, figures 2(b) and (d)). However, they generally yield poor estimations of Atlantic overturning in northernmost areas for all members (figure 2). These varying reconstruction skills across latitudes, indices, and excluded HadGEM3 historical members (figure 2), highlight that basin-scale AMOC variations cannot be adequately characterised with a single index (figure 2). Producing a set of past century AMOC strength variations across several latitudes thus provides a more coherent and robust view of historical AMOC variability. Individual reconstructions and their comparison with other indices in the literature and the AMOC time series from HadGEM3 simulations are provided in figures S8–S11.

We conducted a similar analysis using the six best ESMs instead of relying solely on HadGEM3, excluding all simulations from each of these ESMs (including piControl and SSP1-2.6) from training, one after the other (figure S12). Our conclusions mirror those drawn from the HadGEM3-only analyses (figure S12). From figures 2 and S11, it is evident that ESMs' AMOC time series generated from CNN models are significantly more accurate than previously suggested AMOC indices (Caesar *et al* 2018,

Figure 2. Performance of convolutional neural network (CNN) to reconstruct Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC) time series in HadGEM3 using sea surface temperature (SST) fields, and comparison with other AMOC indices. Reconstructions were performed for 9 different latitudes (from 20° N to 60° N with an increment of 5°) with HadGEM3, the best ESM in terms of simulating observed SST and SSS statistics (figures S3–S6 and table S2). The training set used here is composed of 4 historical runs, and one SSP1-2.6 and piControl runs (table S4). For panels (a)–(d), green circles give the correlation of reconstructed AMOC time series for historical simulation members 1–4 and actual AMOC time series from this same simulation, when it was excluded from the training (materials and methods, table S4), one after the other, for each latitude. Blue circles, orange squares, red diamonds, pink triangles, and purple circles show the correlations between the AMOC time series from the given ESM simulation member with other existing surface-based indices of the AMOC proposed by other studies, i.e. AMOC_{SSS1} through AMOC_{SSS4} (Jackson and Wood 2020, Boers 2021) and AMOC_{SPG} (Caesar *et al* 2018) (materials and methods), respectively.

Jackson and Wood 2020), across all latitudes considered, with improvements consistently significant at the 95% confidence level (figures 2 and S11).

3. Comparison of AMOC reconstructions in historical ESM simulations

To compare the performance of CNN and earlier suggested AMOC indices in historical ESM simulations, we retrained nine new CNN models (one for each latitude of interest, see figures 1 and 2) using all simulations from HadGEM3 (i.e. the best ESM). We applied the same cross-validation scheme as for figure 2 to tune these CNN models, and the optimal sets of batch sizes and initial learning rates were determined for each latitude (table S8). Comparisons were made between the CNN-based AMOC reconstructions and the AMOC results of 51 historical simulations from the 17 ESMs presented in table S1. For reference, we included SST (AMOC_{SPG}) and SSS (AMOC_{SSS1}) indices, with the latter chosen as it performed best among the studied SSS indices when computed within historical simulations (see figures 2 and S12). Figure 3 illustrates that, for all AMOC time series, the reconstructions obtained by applying

CNNs to real data (AMOC_{CNN}) fall within the range of historical simulations. To quantify this, we calculated the number of years between 1900 and 2014 that fall outside of the range described by ESM simulations (table S1). We performed the same calculation for AMOC_{SPG} and AMOC_{SSS1}, as well as for each of the 51 simulations (table S1) where the ESM range for one model simulation is based on the 50 remaining ones (figure 3).

Interestingly, lower latitude AMOC_{CNN} reconstructions (20° N to 30° N) closely align with AMOC_{SPG}, with the latter lagging the former by about 5–10 years. Both time series depict a downward trend from the 1950s (Caesar *et al* 2018), but CNN-based AMOC reconstructions suggest a slight recovery of the AMOC in recent years, consistent with direct RAPID observations (Moat *et al* 2023). This partial recovery is thus expected to continue over the coming years for AMOC_{SPG} (figure 3).

For middle latitudes (35° N and 40° N), the century-long downward trend appears to be less pronounced for 40° N or non-discernible for 35° N. Conversely, at higher latitudes (from 45° N), a downward trend marked by recent record lows is observed, with no visible recovery yet in these regions (figure 3).

Figure 3. Atlantic meridional overturning circulation reconstructions with convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and comparison with other existing surface-based indices and earth system model (ESM) simulations. Reconstructed AMOC time series are provided for 9 different latitudes (from 20° N to 60° N with an increment of 5°), each obtained with a CNN trained and tuned (materials and methods, table S8) using simulations from HadGEM3 (i.e. the less biased ESM from table S2) and applied to observed sea surface temperature (SST) from the HadISST dataset (Rayner *et al* 2003). For each latitude, the left panel gives the normalised and 10-year smoothed reconstructed AMOC time series from the CNN (AMOC_{CNN}, green), and one SST (Caesar *et al* 2018) (AMOC_{SPG}, purple lines) and one SSS (Jackson and Wood 2020, Boers 2021) (AMOC_{SSS1}, orange lines) indices from previous studies (materials and methods), here computed from EN4. Grey shaded areas give the spread of normalised and 10-year smoothed AMOC time series for respective latitudes, computed for 51 historical simulations from 17 CMIP6 ESMs (3 simulation members each, table S1). The ensemble mean of the ESMs' AMOC time series are given by black lines. Right panels give the number of years where AMOC_{CNN} (green dots), AMOC_{SPG} (purple dots), and AMOC_{SPG} (orange dots) fall out of the range drawn by the 51 historical simulations from ESMs (table S1). Grey boxplots give the same out-of-range statistics, when each simulation member from the 51 ensemble is excluded, and where the ESM spread is recomputed from the 50 other simulations.

Consistent with ESMs, the largest decrease at the centennial scale is generally observed for the highest latitudes (figures 1(b) and 3). The increase in sub-polar salinity concentration (captured by AMOC_{SSS1}) from 1950 to 1970, associated with enhanced ocean convection, is recorded in all our reconstructions, albeit with a slight delay at the highest latitudes (figure 3). The second salinity increase through the late 20th century is also associated with a local increase in both AMOC_{CNN} and AMOC_{SPG} time series.

To assess the long-term behaviour of the AMOC across latitudes, we conducted a trend analysis using all 51 historical ESM simulations, the CNN-based reconstructions from observations (AMOC_{CNN}), and the benchmark indices AMOC_{SPG} and AMOC_{SSS1} (figure S13). At the lowest latitudes (20° N–30° N) and at 60° N, AMOC_{CNN} trends lie near the lower end of the ESM range, consistent with the marked decline seen in figure 3. At other latitudes, trends remain negative, though not statistically significant at 35° N and 40° N, and fall within the ensemble range (figure S13). The two reference indices, which do not vary with latitude, show contrasting behaviour: AMOC_{SPG} lies consistently near the bottom of the ESM range, while AMOC_{SSS1} exhibits a positive trend (as in figure S1). The latter agrees with a subset of ESM simulations (figure S13) whose AMOC responds strongly to tropospheric aerosol forcing (Menary *et al* 2020, Robson *et al* 2022). Notably, AMOC_{CNN} trends appear stronger than most ESMs at

20° N–30° N and 60° N. This may reflect the earlier onset of AMOC strengthening in the reconstructions, around the 1950s, linked to increased salinity (as seen in AMOC_{SSS1}), in contrast with the delayed (1980s–1990s) aerosol-driven positive response in many ESM simulations (Menary *et al* 2020).

Overall, the AMOC_{SPG} and AMOC_{SSS1} indices often exhibit values outside the range of ESM simulations for most latitudes (figure 3), likely due to their delayed response and inability to capture AMOC variability across the entire North Atlantic (figures 2 and S12). In contrast, the AMOC_{CNN} reconstructions consistently align better with the range of ESM results (figure 3). While reconstructions at the lowest latitudes may occasionally fall outside the ESM range, they still demonstrate improved agreement compared to previous indices (figure 3). This reconciliation addresses earlier discrepancies between existing estimations of historical AMOC strength and AMOC simulations from ESMs, marking a significant advancement.

4. Comparison with direct AMOC observations

We did not proceed to comparisons of our reconstructions with too short records (less than ten years) from the SAMBA (Meinen *et al* 2013) and OSNAP (Lozier *et al* 2019) arrays. In addition, SAMBA measurements (at 34° S) fall outside our trained CNN domain (0° N–80° N, 80° W–0°,

figure 1(a)). Thus, our analysis focuses on the RAPID time series, compared (figures 4(a) and (b)) with AMOC_{CNN} reconstructions at adjacent latitudes (i.e. 25° N and 30° N). Remarkably, our reconstructions closely match RAPID measurements, capturing the 2009–2010 drop and subsequent partial recovery at the interannual scale (Moat *et al* 2023, figures 4(c) and (d)).

Figures 4(c)–(f) shows the correlation between AMOC time series at 25° N and 30° N and SST fields, based on historical observations from HadISST (Rayner *et al* 2003) and HadGEM3 simulations. As expected, the (linear) relationship between our reconstructed AMOC and SST patterns closely matches that in HadGEM3, since the CNN was trained to infer AMOC variability from SST. This indicates that the physical relationship learned during training also applies to observational data. In line with earlier studies (Rahmstorf *et al* 2015, Caesar *et al* 2018), AMOC–SST correlations under climate change are generally negative at low latitudes on interannual timescales, except in parts of the subpolar North Atlantic where correlations are positive (figures 4(c) and (e)). However, consistent with HadGEM3, the region of positive correlation is shifted southward compared to the AMOC_{SPG} region defined by Caesar *et al* (2018) (figures 4(c)–(f)). Specifically, areas within the Labrador and Irminger seas (used in AMOC_{SPG}) are anticorrelated with our AMOC reconstructions

and with HadGEM3 AMOC at 25° N and 30° N (figures 4(c)–(f)).

5. Conclusions and discussions

Recent findings have raised concerns that the AMOC may be nearing a tipping point, primarily based on surface AMOC indices (Boers 2021, Michel *et al* 2022, Ditlevsen and Ditlevsen 2023). In line with this, we performed an Early Warning Signal (EWS) analysis on our reconstructed AMOC time series (figure S14), using both AR (1) and variance metrics computed over 50 year sliding windows from detrended time series (as in Boers 2021). Significant trends in these indicators were found only for the two northernmost reconstructions (55° N and 60° N), potentially suggesting increased instability. However, the reliability of such metrics is limited when applied to relatively short time series (~120 years). A recent study (Van Westen *et al* 2024) showed that, under such conditions, EWS indicators can yield false positives. This limitation was also highlighted in earlier work using an intermediate-complexity climate model (Boulton *et al* 2014), which found that at least 250 years of data are required for robust detection. While EWSs have been identified in observed surface-based AMOC indices (Boers 2021, Ditlevsen and Ditlevsen 2023) and in a last-millennium machine learning reconstruction (Michel *et al* 2022), the latter offering

greater statistical robustness according to Boulton *et al* (2014), we caution against overinterpreting short-term signals. Furthermore, the most recent and physically grounded assessment of a potential AMOC tipping point, based on South Atlantic salinity transport (Van Westen *et al* 2024), points to a mechanism-based framework not assessable from our reconstructions, which do not capture relevant oceanic transport. Thus, while our results offer limited evidence of EWSs, we consider physically based approaches a more reliable path for assessing AMOC tipping behaviour, in line with recent critiques of statistical EWS metrics (Rietkerk *et al* 2025).

While climate change has already impacted many observables worldwide (Eyring *et al* 2021), the development of historical AMOC time series has long been very controversial (Frajka-Williams *et al* 2019). Disagreements between AMOC reconstructions based on surface indices, ESM simulations, and the direct, but very short, observations from the deep ocean (Cunningham *et al* 2007, Smeed *et al* 2014, McCarthy *et al* 2015, 2018, Moat *et al* 2023), indicate that ESMs were not able to correctly simulate the AMOC, hence casting legitimate doubts on their projections of a future AMOC decline over the twenty-first century. The present study employs advanced deep learning techniques to produce new AMOC indices that align with historical ESM simulations across latitudes from 20° N to 60° N. These results reconcile the longstanding mismatch between AMOC fingerprint proxies (Caesar *et al* 2018, Jackson and Wood 2020, Boers 2021) and ESM simulations (Jackson *et al* 2022), reinforcing confidence in future projections of 21st century AMOC decline (Weijer *et al* 2020).

Data availability statement

All data required to reproduce the study are available online on the following Zenodo link: <https://zenodo.org/records/15368404>. Output data from the study are available online on the same Zenodo link.

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Authors contributions

S.L.L.M. has led the study and was its main designer. S.L.L.M and H.A.D. have co-written the manuscript, managed its production, and determined its scope and purpose. F.G. and V.J.-D. have carried out the deep learning analyses of the study, with systematic contributions and assessments from S.L.L.M. and H.A.D. F.G. and V.J.-D. also contributed to the manuscript writing. R.M.v.W. and A.S.v.d.H. contributed to results' assessments, interpretations, the design of the study, and significantly contributed to the manuscript writing.

Code availability

All codes required to reproduce the study are available online on the following Zenodo link: <https://zenodo.org/records/15368404>.

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References

- Årthun M, Asbjørnsen H, Chafik L, Johnson H L and Våge K 2023 Future strengthening of the Nordic Seas overturning circulation *Nat. Commun.* **14** 2065
- Asbjørnsen H, Eldevik T, Skrefsrud J, Johnson H L and Sanchez-Franks A 2024 Observed change and the extent of coherence in the Gulf Stream system *Ocean Sci.* **20** 799–816
- Bellomo K, Angeloni M, Corti S and von Hardenberg J 2021 Future climate change shaped by inter-model differences in Atlantic meridional overturning circulation response *Nat. Commun.* **12** 3659
- Ben-Yami M, Skiba V, Bathiany S and Boers N 2023 Uncertainties in critical slowing down indicators of observation-based fingerprints of the Atlantic Overturning Circulation *Nat. Commun.* **14** 8344
- Boers N 2021 Observation-based early-warning signals for a collapse of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation *Nat. Clim. Change* **11** 680–8
- Bône C *et al* 2024 Separation of internal and forced variability of climate using a U-Net *James* **16** e2023MS003964
- Booth B B, Dunstone N J, Halloran P R, Andrews T and Bellouin N 2012 Aerosols implicated as a prime driver of twentieth-century North Atlantic climate variability *Nature* **484** 228–32
- Boulton C A, Allison L C and Lenton T M 2014 Early warning signals of Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation collapse in a fully coupled climate model *Nat. Commun.* **5** 5752
- Buckley M W and Marshall J 2016 Observations, inferences, and mechanisms of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation: a review *Rev. Geophys.* **54** 5–63
- Caesar L, Rahmstorf S, Robinson A, Feulner G and Saba V 2018 Observed fingerprint of a weakening Atlantic Ocean overturning circulation *Nature* **556** 191–6
- Chafik L, Holliday N P, Bacon S and Rossby T 2022 Irminger Sea is the center of action for subpolar AMOC variability *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **49** GL099133
- Chafik L and Lozier M S 2025 When simplification leads to ambiguity: a look at two ocean metrics for the subpolar North Atlantic *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **52** e2024GL112496
- Chen H and Tung K-K 2021 Comment on “On the relationship between Atlantic meridional overturning circulation slowdown and global surface warming *Environ. Res. Lett.* **16** 038001
- Collins M *et al* 2019 Extremes, abrupt changes and managing risk *IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate* ed H-O Pörtner *et al* (Cambridge University Press) pp 585–655
- Cunningham S A *et al* 2007 Temporal variability of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation at 26.5° N *Science* **317** 935–8
- Ditlevsen P and Ditlevsen S 2023 Warning of a forthcoming collapse of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation *Nat. Commun.* **14** 4254
- Eyring V, Bony S, Meehl G A, Senior C A, Stevens B, Stouffer R J and Taylor K E 2016 Overview of the coupled model intercomparison project phase 6 (CMIP6) experimental design and organization *Geosci. Model Dev.* **9** 1937–58
- Eyring V *et al* 2021 Human influence on the climate system *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* ed V Masson-Delmotte *et al* (Cambridge University Press) pp 432–552
- Fan Y, Liu W, Zhang P, Chen R and Li L 2023 North Atlantic Oscillation contributes to the subpolar North Atlantic cooling in the past century *Clim. Dyn.* **61** 5199–215
- Frajka-Williams E *et al* 2019 Atlantic meridional overturning circulation: observed transport and variability *Front. Mar. Sci.* **6** 260
- Good S A, Martin M J and Rayner N A 2013 EN4: quality controlled ocean temperature and salinity profiles and monthly objective analyses with uncertainty estimates *J. Geophys. Res.* **118** 6704–16
- Goodfellow I, Bengio Y and Courville A 2016 Convolutional networks *Deep Learning* (MIT Press)
- Ham Y G, Kim J H and Luo J J 2019 Deep learning for multi-year ENSO forecasts *Nature* **573** 568–72
- Jackson L C, Biastoch A, Buckley M W, Desbruyères D G, Frajka-Williams E, Moat B and Robson J 2022 The evolution of the North Atlantic meridional overturning circulation since 1980 *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.* **3** 241–54
- Jackson L C and Wood R A 2020 Fingerprints for early detection of changes in the AMOC *J. Clim.* **33** 7027–44
- Jacques-Dumas V, Ragone F, Borgnat P, Abry P and Bouchet F 2022 Deep learning-based extreme heatwave forecast *Front. Clim.* **4** 789641
- Knight J R, Allan R J, Folland C K, Vellinga M and Mann M E 2005 A signature of persistent natural thermohaline circulation cycles in observed climate *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **32** L20708
- Latif M, Sun J, Visbeck M and Hadi Bordbar M 2022 Natural variability has dominated Atlantic meridional overturning circulation since 1900 *Nat. Clim. Change* **12** 455–60
- Little C M, Zhao M and Buckley M W 2020 Do surface temperature indices reflect centennial-timescale trends in Atlantic meridional overturning circulation strength? *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **47** GL090888
- Liu W, Xie S-P, Liu Z and Zhu J 2017 Overlooked possibility of a collapsed Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation in warming climate *Sci. Adv.* **3** e1601666
- Lozier M S *et al* 2019 A sea change in our view of overturning in the subpolar North Atlantic *Science* **363** 516–21
- Mann M E, Steinman B A, Brouillette D J and Miller S K 2021 Multidecadal climate oscillations during the past millennium driven by volcanic eruptions *Science* **371** 1014–9
- McCarthy G D, Smeed D A, Johns W E, Frajka-Williams E, Moat B I, Rayner D, Baringer M O, Meinen C S, Collins J and Bryden H L 2015 measuring the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation at 26° N *Progr. Oceanogr.* **130** 91–111
- Meinen C S, Speich S, Perez R C, Dong S, Piola A R, Garzoli S L, Baringer M O, Gladyshev S and Campos E J D 2013 Temporal variability of the meridional overturning circulation at 34.5° S: results from two pilot boundary arrays in the South Atlantic *J. Geophys. Res.* **118** 6461–79
- Menary M B *et al* 2020 Aerosol-forced AMOC changes in CMIP6 historical simulations *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **47** GL088166
- Michel S L L, Swingedouw D, Ortega P, Gastineau G, Mignot J, McCarthy G and Khodri M 2022 Early warning signal for a tipping point suggested by a millennial Atlantic Multidecadal Variability reconstruction *Nat. Commun.* **13** 5176
- Moat B I *et al* 2023 Atlantic meridional overturning circulation observed by the RAPID-MOCHA-WBTS (RAPID-Meridional Overturning Circulation and Heatflux Array-Western Boundary Time Series) array at 26N from 2004 to 2022 (v2022.1) *British Oceanographic Data Centre—Natural Environment Research Council, UK* (<https://doi.org/10.5285/04c79ece-3186-349a-e063-6c86abc0158c>)
- Rahmstorf S, Box J E, Feulner G, Mann M E, Robinson A, Rutherford S and Schaffernicht E J 2015 Exceptional twentieth-century slowdown in Atlantic Ocean overturning circulation *Nat. Clim. Change* **5** 475–80
- Rayner N A, Parker D E, Horton E B, Folland C K, Alexander I V, Rowell D P, Kent E C and Kaplan A 2003 Global analyses of sea surface temperature, sea ice, and night marine air temperature since the late nineteenth century *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* **108** 4407
- Rietkerk M, Skiba V, Weinans E, Hébert R and Laepple T 2025 Ambiguity of early warning signals for climate tipping points *Nat. Clim. Change* **15** 479–88
- Robson J, Menary M B, Sutton R T, Mecking J, Gregory J M, Jones C, Sinha B, Stevens D P and Wilcox L J 2022 The role of anthropogenic aerosol forcing in the 1850–1985

- strengthening of the AMOC in CMIP6 historical simulations *J. Clim.* **35** 6843–63
- Rosby T, Palter J and Donohue K 2022 What can hydrography between the New England slope, Bermuda and Africa tell us about the strength of the AMOC over the last 90 years? *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **49** GL099173
- Smeed D A *et al* 2014 Observed decline of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation 2004–2012 *Ocean Sci.* **10** 29–38
- Smeed D A *et al* 2018 The North Atlantic Ocean is in a state of reduced overturning *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **45** 1527–33
- Swingedouw D, Houssais M-N and Herbault C 2022 AMOC recent and future trends: a crucial role for oceanic respiration and Greenland melting? *Fron. Clim.* **4** 838310
- Van Westen R M, Kliphuis M and Dijkstra H A 2024 Physics-based early warning signal shows that AMOC is on tipping course *Sci. Adv.* **10** eadk1189
- Weijer W, Cheng W, Garuba O A, Hu A and Nadiga B T 2020 CMIP6 models predict significant 21st century decline of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **47** GL086075
- Worthington E L, Moat B I, Smeed D A, Mecking J V, Marsh R and McCarthy G D 2021 A 30 year reconstruction of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation shows no decline *Ocean Sci.* **17** 285–99
- Zhang R, Sutton R, Danabasoglu G, Kwon Y-O, Marsh R, Yeager S G, Amrhein D E and Little C M 2019 A review of the role of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation in Atlantic multidecadal variability and associated climate impacts *Rev. Geophys.* **57** 316–75
- Zou S, Lozier S and Xu X 2020 Latitudinal structure of the meridional overturning circulation variability on interannual to decadal time scales in the North Atlantic Ocean *J. Clim.* **33** 3845–62